

Dalit Conversion and Reservation Demand: Some Questions

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Introduction:

India remained barbaric until the arrival of the Westerners; the British called themselves a '*civilization mission*' to civilize Indians. Through this, they not only launched a huge project to convert Indians, but also created new programs to criticize Indian society and culture. It is equally true that Christian ideas were passed on to Indians in the name of education and literature, when the process of conversion mainly through missionaries did not meet the expected success. It is a fact that Dalit communities are at the forefront of conversion victims in this entire process.

'Hindu society is corrupt; the story that Dalit's have been subjected to exploitation and brutality for centuries is an important source of conversion. Christianity, Islam is religions that preach 'equality' and the solution to discrimination, exploitation, oppression and problems of Dalit's are to convert to them. Also another way to solve the problems of Dalit's is reservation. Here is something to note: Dalits already have a tendency to claim reservation even after conversion. A demand to legislate it has been put before the government. The central government is waiting for the report of appointing Balakrishna Committee. In this context, this article is a small attempt to review the debate surrounding the Dalit reservation demand of these converts.

This article consists of two main parts. First, who are a Dalit Christian and a Dalit Muslim? The pros and cons of the question whether they should be given reservation or not are analysed. Second, would the demand for reservation for converts not be an injustice to actual Dalits? The reactions of Dalit organizations and thinkers have been analysed.

Part-I

Conversion of Dalits and Caste Reservation- Committees & Recommendations:

There is no mistaking the fact that India is a dual-colonial state. One is the rule of Islam and the other is European rule. In both these cases we see Indians being converted indiscriminately. During the Muslim rule, it was considered a meritorious act to convert the infidels of India to Islam, while the British rule concluded that it was our duty to lead the Indian Hindus in the 'darkness' to the 'light'.

In both cases, the worst narratives about Indian society, about caste, were created. He said that some communities here are low castes, like slaves in European countries; the Hindu society has been exploiting and atrocious on them in the past. He said conversion is the way to save them. It is not limited to the colonial period but is still relevant today. Processes of converting Dalit castes to Islam and Christianity are taking place. Even after conversion they are called 'Dalit Muslims' and 'Dalit Christians' instead of Muslims and Christians. But how can they become 'Dalit' even after conversion?

Conversion and Reservation: Pros and Cons

Is it right to give them reservation after conversion or not? Questions have already been raised. Suggestions were received by forming some committees. It is true that there were some pro-opposition discussions around that.

Supporting Reservation for converttees:

According to the Constitution (Scheduled Castes) Order 1950, only marginalized groups/communities professing Hinduism, Sikhism and Buddhism can become members of Scheduled Castes. Originally, only Hindus were eligible for reservation under the Scheduled Caste quota, but Sikhs were included in 1956 and Buddhists in 1990. Communities/castes of other religions cannot be included in the list of Scheduled Castes. This means that Muslim and Christian groups are effectively barred from being included in the list of converted SCs.¹

¹ <https://tinyurl.com/2ayd92wl> (last Seen 17-5-2024)

Committees and Recommendations:

1. Ranganath Mishra Committee:

The committee was constituted in 2004 under the chairmanship of former Chief Justice Ranganath Mishra and named as the National Commission for Religious and Linguistic Minorities. It is also known as Ranganatha Mishra Commission. After nearly 4 years of survey they submitted the report on 21st May, 2007 to Govt. In this report, Dalit Christians and Muslims face discrimination not only from upper-caste members of their own religion, but also from the wider Hindu-dominated society. Exclusion of Dalits from the SC category for converting into Christianity and Islam violates the constitutional guarantee of equality. It is against the basic tenets of these religions to reject caste discrimination. Also the denial of SC status to Dalits who have converted to Christianity and Islam led to their socio-economic and educational backwardness and were deprived of access to reservations (provided under Article 16) in education and employment opportunities.

There was strong opposition to this recommendation. Also, this report led the BJP to file a PIL against the report which recommended Scheduled Quotas for all minorities, including Dalits, Christians and Muslims. The Centre decided that the Justice Ranganath Mishra Commission report, which favoured extending the benefits of reservation to Dalits who had converted to Islam and Christianity, was written without any field study and communicated this decision to the Supreme Court.²

2. Rajendra Sachar Committee:

The UPA government constituted a seven-member high-level committee in 2005 headed by former Chief Justice of the High Court Rajendra Sachar. Its main task is to study the social, economic and educational status of Muslims. This committee submitted its report in 2009. It observed that the social and economic condition of Dalits did not improve after conversion. The committee presented its report in two Houses. But these recommendations were not accepted as the report had inadequate field data and failed to corroborate with actual situation, the two houses said.³ There was a strong demand for reservation for Dalit Christians, and the report of the appointed committees could not be accepted as not providing adequate explanations.

² <https://tinyurl.com/26d9gj5k> (last Seen 17-5-2024)

³ <https://forumias.com/blog/sachar-committee/> (last Seen 17-5-2024)

3. K. G. Balakrishnan Committee:

The Commission was appointed by the Central Government in 2022 under KG Balakrishnan, former Chief Justice of India and former Chairman of the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC). A three-member commission headed by K G Balakrishnan and it includes a retired IAS officer Dr. Ravindra Kumar Jain and University Grants Commission member Prof. Sushma Yadav. The committee aims to submit its report within two years. Its objectives are 1. Examining the issue of whether Scheduled Caste (SC) status can be granted to Dalits who have converted over many years to other than Sikh or Buddhist religion. 2. The commission's inquiry will also examine the changes that occur after the person converts into another religion and the consequences of treating them as scheduled castes. One of the important observations of the reports of these committees is that there is no change in the status of Dalits who have converted to other religions. And the converttees are facing new problems after conversion. If this is true, it needs to be checked whether conversion is a solution to the problems of Dalits.⁴

After converting to religions, they are facing more problems. “Forgetting the foundation of Christianity and opposing the principles of love, charity, brotherhood etc., our fellow Christians see us as untouchable even in our churches. They make sure we don't come close. A separate seating system, an iron gate separating them from others at the gathering places, a barrier wall of cane slats, and a fence will be constructed. There are many such churches, in the reception of the sacraments, there is a strange separation practiced in order to ward off pollution.”⁵

“Though our Christianity teaches the basic principles of human equality in the sight of God, the need for charity, love for neighbour, mutual cooperation and kindness, many of us, converted from your class, remain, even today, in a poor condition like your class of Hindus. Many things are most important because of the casteism and missionary neglect of the dominant Hindu mentality lack of authority, disorder etc. among some converttees of the Christianity, we remain as Christian untouchables even today as we were before Christianity.”⁶

⁴ <https://optimizeias.com/justice-balakrishnan-commission/> (last Seen 17-5-2024)

⁵ Writings and Speeches of Dr BR Ambedkar. Volume-4. 2010. Kuvempu Bhasha Bharati Pradhikari. p. 480. Bangalore.

⁶ Writings and Speeches of Dr BR Ambedkar. Volume-4. 2010. Kuvempu Bhasha Bharati Pradhikari. p. 462. Bangalore.

“Caste rituals are common in churches. That is, separate burials and separate seats for upper castes and lower castes during worship, such discrimination continues unabated in Hinduism as well as in Christianity. Intermarriage and exchange of food between upper and lower castes is strictly prohibited. Young men and women of lower castes are also discriminated against in appointment as priests. This has led to frustration and anger among the lower caste Christians.”

Many thinkers are of the same opinion. The solution is zero because the conversion of religions is bound to scare away the original problems again and again. Above all, the premise that Dalit converttees should stay away from public life and that they should get reservation after conversion has given rise to further conflicts.

Objections to reservation for converttees:

The British did not come to India just to rule, who came here to spread their religion. For that, he dealt with oppression, untouchability and harassment in Indian society. They produced their own story of Indian social structure as a caste system. In this they emphasized that Brahmins were superior and untouchables inferior. Interpreting Brahmins as Catholic priests (pagan priests) and blaming them for all the calamities here, those identified as lower castes were interpreted as slaves of mediaeval Europe and attributed their characteristics to some of the caste groups in India.

By that, Dalits were thought of as barbarians and oppressed. The Christian missionaries, the British rulers felt that it was their responsibility to bring them to the light of darkness. So the ways to become a citizen are; one, conversion; two, getting western education. Missionaries tried both of them. There is nothing wrong in saying that they were more successful in the latter by building educational institutions. They have started teaching English in it; they have designed curricula for many years; curricula directly connected with western ideas that are influenced by Christian ideas. Western ideas built a hateful attitude in educated Indians to reject their original traditions and practices as immoral, corrupt, and unscientific(S. N. Balagangadhar). Apart from that, they started housing, hospitals and medical facilities in the name of service. By giving all these they succeeded in converting Dalits.

Western pastor Mögling says, “I think the goal of missionaries is to understand the spirit of the people in front of us and to get rid of traditional ideas. He feels that it is our first duty as

missionaries to liberate people from misunderstanding material ideas and form a new way of thinking” (Herman Mögling. “Missionary Pravasa” 2022. 4).

Thus, the converttees succeed in getting education, health and other benefits, it is not justified to continue the reservation provided to them constitutionally. Also, giving reservation to those who reject the original caste, tradition, and practices and follow a different path is not like giving an aid to the prosperity of Dalits? This is the reason many people oppose the reservation for converttees.

Part-II

Reservation for converttees: Dalit perspective

History shows that Christian missionaries first tried to convert the upper castes in India, but failed to do so. Therefore their target shifted to the Dalit communities. It is true that they were partially successful in the process of proselytization. Constitutional governance in independent India provided a way for the backward communities to be empowered and redress their problems by giving reservation. But the reason for giving this reservation is,

Westerners' understanding of India is like this: “the three stages of the Vedic religion, Brahmanism and Hinduism were mainly responsible for the decline and loss of excellence of the religion in India. The Vedic religion retained the original messages of God (like Biblical); Brahmanism became corrupt and degenerate as the Brahmin purohita (like priest); it was 'Hinduism' which was corrupted by Brahmanism, which was already corrupt, and went on the path of destruction.”(S. N., Balagangadhara,)

This quote makes it clear that the caste system was born out of corrupt Hinduism due to which certain communities were backward and reservation was implemented for the empowerment of those communities. Corrupt Hinduism led to the birth of the caste system. The caste system is responsible for the present day plight of Dalit communities. So is it appropriate to extend the constitutional opportunities reserved for Dalits within Hindu society to those outside Hinduism? What was Ambedkar's position on the conversion of Dalits to these Christian and Muslim religions? This second question may be more helpful in answering the first question.

Ambedkar and Religious Conversion:

Ambedkar was a leader who was very concerned about Dalit communities. He worked day and night to find solutions to the problems of Dalits. He strongly advocated the path of empowerment using reservation. Although it is true that he eventually joined Buddhism, he strongly advocated that conversion to Christianity and Islam would not solve the problems of Dalits. As Ambedkar says: "Christianity propagandists never thought it was their duty to eliminate the atrocities and injustices on the Dalits after conversion... Above all, after conversion, the Dalits became helpless instead of resisting the atrocities against them"⁷ (BR Ambedkar, 2010: 480).

Also opposes conversion to Islam and points the way towards Buddhism. The reason for his stance may be that Buddhism is not a religion as such but an Indian tradition. So, it is a kind of disrespect to Ambedkar that Dalits who worship Ambedkar are converting into Christianity. In a sense, Ambedkar's position on conversion to Semitic religions like Christianity and Islam shows that reservations to the convertees is not justifiable.

Dalits converted to Christianity with the intention of raising their social and educational status. If the inequality of the Hindu society and the caste society is addressed, the reason they give for conversion is that the Christian religion will be merciful to the new status, and it is their duty to make an effort to empower them. It is a big mistake to call them 'Dalit Christians' despite their conversion. They are only Christians or Muslims upon conversion. Not Dalits. Therefore, the argument is there from dalit perspective that it is not the right decision to give reservation to Christians who have converted from caste society.

As long as the reservation is there, it is said that till the caste system is destroyed. If caste system is a feature of Hindu society, shouldn't reservation be given only to Hindu society? It should be noted that the reservation given to Christians and Muslims should be excluded from the social reservation. Because as they say. There is no caste system, inequality, untouchability in Islam and Christianity. If so, why extend reservation to them?

Reservation for convertees and injustice to Dalits:

We see Dalit communities living in their own castes whether it is pain or pleasure. Ambedkar has proposed to give reservation for their benefit and it is constitutional and just that

⁷ Writings and Speeches of Dr BR Ambedkar. Volume-4. 2010. Kuvempu Bhasha Bharati Pradhikari. p. 480. Bangalore.

reservation should reach them. But it is ironic that against their wishes and the purpose of the reservation policy, the reservation that should be given to the poor and backward Dalits is going to the rich Dalits and converttees. Converttees get better education in Christian educational institutions, already occupy government jobs using reservation, and are successful in getting Scheduled reservation for them by getting better connections through Church and other institutions. This is a real injustice and cruelty to the actual/common Dalits. So, giving reservation to converttees is a big deception for Dalit communities. Showing Dalits living in huts and shacks and taking away their share of reservation is not only anti-Dalit, anti-Ambedkar but also anti-constitutional.

There are many organizations across the country that claim to be pro-Dalit. Many organizations exist in the country in the name of human rights. But they are unaware of the huge injustice being done to the common Dalits. In some places these organizations are knowingly or unknowingly harming the interests of Dalits by fighting for reservation for Dalit Christians. So doubts arise whether some Dalit organizations are in favour of the real Dalits, are they complementary to Ambedkar's wish, and are they committed to the position of the Constitution? Many are already away from their castes, away from traditions, even though they are Christians, they have got reservations on the basis of their previous castes (SC, ST) and have been availing the facilities for generations. Unfortunately, most of the organizations and progressive thinkers are involved in supporting them, instead of raising their voices on this issue. The basic aim of reservation is to uplift and empower the real Dalits and the backward. It is everyone's duty to ensure that those who retain their traditional identity despite their hardships and hardships get the opportunities of reservation. If not, these next questions should be taken seriously.

1. It should be noted that, if religious converttees are given reservation, will they use it to further criticise Indian society and culture in a western perspective?
2. If reservation is meant to eradicate the inequality and untouchability of the Hindu society, then limiting it to the Hindu communities alone, is not legitimate?
3. Many people are still getting their previous caste certificates even though they have been converted long ago. Observing these will be a real pro-Dalit concern. But pro-Dalit organizations and thinkers are doing the opposite. Will the effective implementation of the Anti-Conversion Bill be a partial solution in this regard? It has to be looked at seriously.

4. Isn't the demand to take away the privileges of Dalits and give them to someone else (Christians) not only anti-Dalit but also anti-Ambedkar and anti-constitutional? The question must be asked.

5. After conversion they are all Christians and not Dalit Christians. The concept that Dalits are Christians is wrong. If the problems of Dalits will increase even after they convert to Christianity, should we stop the claims that conversion is a solution and that there is exploitation and atrocities only in Hindu society? Or time to reconsider those propositions.

It should be noted that all these questions provide a platform for serious thought and discussion. An attempt has been made so far to analyse the debate and problems surrounding the extension of reservation to converttees.

Conclusion:

Overall, it is not the intention of this article to enjoin that no reservation should be given to Dalit converttees and no support should be given to the religious conversion. Also, we are not suggesting that thinkers and activists should not support it. The assumption that conversion to religions is the path to liberation is denying justice to Dalits. It is imperative to understand that asking for reservation for the converttees in such a context raises some serious logical questions. Article shows that proselytizing and supporting conversion without understanding the agenda of religions is a threat to Dalits and Ambedkar's hope. It is more appropriate to re-examine Babu Jagjivan Ram's statement that if one has an intention to stay away from social ills, it is better to stay in that society and correct it.

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